

BIOBASEDCERT

Mid-term Clustering Report for HORIZON – CL6-2021- ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07

Joint Deliverable

This deliverable is an output of the joint work of HARMONITOR, STAR4BBS and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D7.4 (HARMONITOR) 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D7.4 (STAR4BBS) 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D6.5 (SUSTCERT4BIOBASED) 	

Technical references

Cluster Name	BiobasedCert
Cluster Title	Enhancing Sustainability Certification Schemes and Labels for Bio-based Systems
Cluster Composition	<p>HARMONITOR (101060133) www.harmonitor.eu</p> <p>STAR4BBS (101060588) www.sustcert4biobased.eu</p> <p>SUSTCERT4BIOBASED (101059785) www.star4bbs.eu</p>
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Deliverable No.	D7.4 (HARMONITOR) / D7.4 (STAR4BBS) / D6.5 (SUSTCERT4BIOBASED)
Dissemination level	Public
Due date of deliverable	30 November 2023
Actual submission date	30 November 2023
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Documentary History

V	Date	Description
0.1	18/10/2023	First draft
0.2	22/11/2023	Reviewed and revised version
0.3	27/11/2023	Consolidated version
0.4	29/11/2023	Final version

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List of Acronyms

B2B	Business-2-business
CBA	Costs and benefits analysis
CSLs	Sustainability Certifications Schemes and Labels
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
HRB	Horizon Results Booster
IPTs	Inter-project teams
JAB	Joint Advisory Board
JMS	Joint Monitoring System
POs	Project Officers
PCs	Project Coordinators
REA	European Research Executive Agency
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The call "Clean environment and zero pollution (HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01)" sought proposals to support the development of climate-neutral circular bio-based systems that aim to establish a zero-pollution economy in line with the 2030 Climate Target Plan and Zero Pollution ambition. The focus is on enhancing transparency in international and EU trade for bio-based materials and products through certification schemes and business-to-business (B2B) labels. Proposals were expected to review and analyse existing certification schemes, assess their effectiveness, and analyse costs associated with their adoption in industrial bio-based value chains. Additionally, the call encouraged cooperation with international partners and organisations. The goal is to promote sustainable practices in the bio-based industry and contribute to environmental, social, and economic well-being.

The projects selected under the call "ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07: International and EU sustainability certification schemes for bio-based systems" include STAR4BBS (Sustainability Transition Assessment Rules for Bio-Based Systems), HARMONITOR (Harmonisation and monitoring platform for certification schemes and labels to advance the sustainability of bio-based systems), and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED (Sustainability Certification for Biobased Systems). These three sister projects have formed a project cluster named BiobasedCert.

This report aims to:

- i) highlight the added value and purpose of the cluster;
- ii) summarise different clustering activities among the aforementioned three projects implemented during the first eighteen months;
- iii) provide an overview and explanation of upcoming joint activities aiming to further strengthen the ties between the three projects.

The deliverable covers work jointly conducted within the identified strategic areas of importance of the three sister projects and related cooperation activities in each area. Most prominently, the establishment of a Joint Advisory Board, the development of a Joint Monitoring System, and collaboration in inter-project thematic areas are described in detail. The report builds on the close and ongoing collaboration of the three projects coordinators and the different inter-project teams.

The purpose of this deliverable is to report on the established collaborative approach of the three projects. This is done by outlining the cooperation activities that align the goals of the respective projects, avoid duplication of efforts, maximise impact, and facilitate the exchange of information and expertise.

1. Introduction

1.1. Overview of the Cluster and of the three projects awarded to address the HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07 call

The HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07 call – "International and EU sustainability certification schemes for bio-based systems" centers around supporting tracing of environmental, social and economic impacts along value chains and trades in the bio-based systems for business-to-business (B2B) communication to enable responsible production and consumption, in line with the 2030 Climate Target Plan and the Zero Pollution ambition. This call sought contribution to establishing circular bio-based systems to mitigate climate change, restore biodiversity and protect air, soil and water quality along the supply chain of biological resources and industrial value chains, within the EU and across borders. These topics align with several impact areas identified in the Horizon Europe strategic plan for 2021-2024. Project results are expected to contribute to the following expected outcomes: (I) bio-based value chains transparency in international and EU trade through B2B labels for biological resources and bio-based materials and products, and (II) harmonisation of existing international and EU certification schemes and the monitoring system and indicators of their effectiveness and robustness.

Projects funded under this topic include STAR4BBS (Sustainability Transition Assessment Rules for Bio-Based Systems), HARMONITOR (Harmonisation and monitoring platform for certification schemes and labels to advance the sustainability of bio-based systems) and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED (Sustainability Certification for Biobased Systems). These three sister projects have formed a project cluster named BiobasedCert.

The objectives of the cluster are following:

- Gain a precise picture of existing **sustainability certification schemes** and **labels**;
- Gather specific **global trade data** and information on **volumes** of biological feedstock and bio-based materials and products, differentiating between certified and uncertified flows;
- **Develop** and **test a monitoring system** to assess the effectiveness and robustness of existing sustainability certifications schemes and labels (CSLs);
- Explore the impact on the adoption of sustainability CSLs on market access and trade within bio-based systems, performing a **feasibility study** on B2B labels;
- **Develop** and **disseminate** findings and recommendations to promote the adoption of effective and robust sustainability CSLs by different categories of stakeholders.

The identified three Joint Strategic Areas are:

- Joint Advisory board
- Joint Monitoring System
- Joint Dissemination

The STAR4BBS (www.star4bbs.eu) project aims to maximise the potential of sustainability CSLs to support a successful transition to a sustainable bio-based economy. It entails the development of indicators and a monitoring system for assessing the effectiveness and robustness of existing international and EU CSLs, B2B labels and related traceability systems applicable to biological feedstock and bio-based materials and products. This will create the foundations to support transparency and scheme harmonisation in global and EU trade flows.

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED (www.sustcert4biobased.eu) project is set on defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust CSLs and B2B labels for industrial biobased systems. This supports the overall goal of supporting responsible production and consumption by tracing the sustainability of biobased products along value chains and trades within the EU and globally.

The HARMONITOR (www.harmonitor.eu) project aims to improve the effectiveness of CSLs in different sectors of the EU bioeconomy and therefore strengthen the use of CSLs as a co-regulation instrument. Effective and robust CSLs can cope with some of the difficulties that public regulation faces and fill in policy gaps. The HARMONITOR project is devoted to establishing and testing a participative review platform concept that allows CSLs to identify commonalities and foster cooperation when operating in bio-based value chains within and across EU borders.

1.2. Purpose of this deliverable

To ensure that the three projects work together effectively, a coordinated and collaborative approach is essential. This deliverable outlines several cooperation activities that the projects are undertaking to align their goals, avoid duplication of efforts, and maximise their impact. The work of sister projects is jointly conducted within the identified strategic areas for the three projects and related cooperation activities in each area.

The cooperation activities include thematic area discussions and decision-making, establishing a Joint Monitoring System (JMS), exchanging information and data, establishing a Joint Advisory Board (JAB), coordinating common activities, and collaborating in the dissemination and communication of findings. By working together and coordinating efforts, the three projects are ensuring that their work is aligned, complementary, and contributes to the overall goal of promoting sustainability in bio-based systems.

The coordination and management of the cluster activities is overseen by the three project coordinators (PCs). The PCs are responsible for ensuring that the cluster activities are carried out effectively and efficiently and that they are aligned with the goals and strategies of the three sister projects.

To facilitate the cooperation activities, five thematic inter-project teams have been established, each consisting of institutions and researchers from the three sister projects. These inter-project teams are focusing on five thematic areas: selection and review of CSLs; bio-based value chain selection and global trade flows; Joint Monitoring System; analysis of costs and benefits and feasibility study; communication and dissemination of the results. Within each area, synergies and cooperation opportunities are identified by the sister projects. By working together through the inter-project teams and under the guidance of the PCs, the three projects are making sure that their efforts are aligned and complementary, maximising their impact on the EU's sustainability goals.

2. Integrated strategic collaboration

2.1. Added value of the collaboration

The following areas were identified as offering significant added value to the collaboration of the sister projects:

1. **Efficient resource utilisation:** The sister projects can pool resources, expertise, and data. This allows for a more efficient use of resources and infrastructure. This shared resource pool can lead to cost savings and optimised research efforts.
2. **Reduced duplication:** By working together, sister projects can avoid duplicating research, development, and data collection efforts. This minimises redundancy, optimises the use of resources, and accelerates progress toward common objectives.
3. **Synergy and innovation:** Collaborative efforts often lead to the generation of novel ideas, methodologies, and solutions. The collective expertise and diverse perspectives from multiple and diverse project teams can spark innovation and creative problem-solving.
4. **Comprehensive approach:** Sister projects can address complex challenges from multiple angles. By combining their efforts, they can provide a more comprehensive and holistic understanding of the issues at hand, leading to more robust solutions.
5. **Enhanced impact:** Collaboration amplifies the influence and reach of the research, thereby contributing more effectively to the overarching goals.
6. **Improved knowledge transfer:** Collaborative projects facilitate the exchange of knowledge and best practices among research teams. This knowledge transfer ensures that insights, findings, and innovations are disseminated more widely, benefiting a broader audience.
7. **Strengthened advocacy:** When sister projects work together, they can present a united front when advocating for policy changes or promoting their findings.
8. **Risk mitigation:** Collaboration can help mitigate the risks associated with research and innovation projects. If one project encounters challenges or setbacks, others can step in to offer support or alternative solutions, reducing overall project risk.
9. **Interdisciplinary integration:** Collaboration encourages the integration of different disciplinary perspectives. This cross-disciplinary approach can lead to more holistic, well-rounded solutions that account for various aspects of complex issues.
10. **Scalability and universality:** Research findings and solutions developed through collaborative projects are often more scalable and more widely applicable, as they have been tested and refined in multiple contexts and under various conditions.

2.2. Structure of collaboration

2.2.1. Thematic areas for inter-project collaboration

To facilitate the collaboration, five thematic areas were identified for inter-project collaboration. Within each of the identified thematic areas, the inter-project team aims to look for synergies and cooperation opportunities among the three projects. Meetings and discussions with sister projects teams on these five thematic areas are organised to share information, align goals and strategies, and identify opportunities for collaboration. The aim is to avoid duplication of effort and achieve greater impact through coordinated efforts.

The three projects coordinate their activities to ensure that they are aligned and complementary. This includes aligning key activities, such as research, data collection, and stakeholder engagement as well as reporting on progress to other inter-project team members.

The five identified thematic areas are shown in Figure 1 and described in more detail in the text below.

Figure 1: Five thematic areas of the inter-project collaboration

A. Selection and review of CSLs

The team for this area is responsible for establishing synergies in the selection and review of existing CSLs. It also reviews existing monitoring systems and benchmarking platforms with the purpose of identifying building blocks for the design of the Joint Monitoring System.

B. Value chain selection and trade flows

The team in this area aims to identify synergies in the analysis of global trade flows of biological feedstock and bio-based materials and products. Additionally, they are responsible for coordinating the identification and selection of the most prominent biobased value chains.

C. Joint Monitoring System (JMS)

The three projects work together to develop a JMS to assess the robustness and effectiveness of CSLs. Following the acceptance of the proposed JMS by the EU officials whereby the three projects jointly work on the development of the monitoring system, the inter-project teams started working on identifying synergies in the conceptualization, development and testing of the JMS. The JMS is collaboratively designed to meet the needs of stakeholders and to facilitate the exchange of information and data. The JMS will also help to identify best practices, monitor progress towards sustainability goals, and enable more effective decision-making.

D. Costs and benefits analysis (CBA) and feasibility study

The inter-project team collaborating within this thematic area works on aligning on methodologies for the quantification of direct and indirect costs and benefits of certification, as well as on assessing the feasibility of selected CSLs.

E. Communication and dissemination

The communications team works on the planning and implementation of the joint communication, exploitation and dissemination activities. The aim is to capitalise on established outcomes by developing a strong network through joint activities and by participating in various events.

In addition to the previously specified thematic areas, the three projects are committed to supporting each other in the design and implementation of the activities specific to each project but that are beneficial to other projects as well. For example, STAR4BBS and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED collaborated with HARMONITOR by providing inputs and disseminating the public consultation on sustainability certification of bio-based products, launched at the end of February 2023.

2.2.2. Teamwork architecture

The cluster of the three projects includes: project coordinators (PCs) and inter-project teams (IPTs).

- Project Coordinators (PCs)

The three PCs are responsible for the overall coordination and management of the cluster activities. In addition, they are responsible for direct communication with the Project Officers (POs) at the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Table 1 shows the PCs for each sister project.

Table 1: PC representatives

Project	Name of Coordinator	Institution
HARMONITOR	Sergio Ugarte Costanza Rossi	SQ Consult B.V.
STAR4BBS	Luana Ladu	Technische Universität Berlin (TUB)
SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	Iris Vural Gursel	Stichting Wageningen Research (WR)

- Inter-project teams (IPTs)

The role of the five IPTs is to collaborate within the aforementioned strategic areas on the topics for which they already have responsibilities leading tasks and/or work packages (WPs) in their own projects, as well as identifying synergies and cooperation opportunities among the three projects. Table 2 show the current members of the inter-project teams from all three projects, according to the thematic areas.

Table 2: Inter-project teams

First Name	Last Name	Affiliation	Affiliation abbreviation	Project or Project Role	Theme(s) Assigned
Jurjen	Spekreijse	Biomass Technology Group	BTG	HARMONITOR	Value chain selection & Trade Flows
Marisa	Groenestege	Biomass Technology Group	BTG	HARMONITOR	Value chain selection & Trade Flows
Martijn	Vis	Biomass Technology Group	BTG	HARMONITOR	Value chain selection & Trade Flows
Stefan	Majer	DBFZ	DBFZ	HARMONITOR	JMS, Selection and review of CSLs
Beike	Sumfleth	DBFZ	DBFZ	HARMONITOR	Selection and review of CSLs
Hando	Hain	Preferred by Nature	PbN	HARMONITOR	Selection and review of CSLs

The HARMONITOR, STAR4BBS and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED projects have received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme

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Simon	Møller	Preferred by Nature	PbN	HARMONITOR	Selection and review of CSLs; CBA & Feasibility Study
Birka	Wicke	Radboud University	RU	HARMONITOR	CBA & Feasibility Study
Sergio	Ugarte	SQ Consult	SQ	HARMONITOR	Communication & Dissemination
Monique	Voogt	SQ Consult	SQ	HARMONITOR	Dissemination and Communication
Costanza	Rossi	SQ Consult; Utrecht University	SQ; UU	HARMONITOR	Dissemination and Communication; CBA & Feasibility Study
Li	Shen	Utrecht University	UU	HARMONITOR	JMS
Michele	Mutчек	Utrecht University	UU	HARMONITOR	JMS
Martin	Junginger	Utrecht University	UU	HARMONITOR	JMS
Maulidia	Khairani	Utrecht University	UU	HARMONITOR	JMS

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Stefano	Lauro	RINA	RINA	HARMONITOR	CBA & Feasibility Study
Matilde	Festi	RINA	RINA	HARMONITOR	CBA & Feasibility Study
Elena	Rocco	RINA	RINA	HARMONITOR	CBA & Feasibility Study
Laura	Magnasco	RINA	RINA	HARMONITOR	CBA & Feasibility Study
Laura	Severino	RINA	RINA	HARMONITOR	CBA & Feasibility Study
Matthias	Grill	AgroVet	AGR	HARMONITOR	CBA & Feasibility Study
Franciska	Radic	GRAS	GRAS	HARMONITOR	JMS
Apostolis	Koutinas	Agricultural University of Athens	AUA	STAR4BBS	CBA & Feasibility Study
Dimitrios	Ladakis	Agricultural University of Athens	AUA	STAR4BBS	CBA & Feasibility Study

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Sofia Maria	Ioannidou	Agricultural University of Athens	AUA	STAR4BBS	Value chain selection & Trade Flows; CBA & Feasibility Study
Stamatia	Skoutida	Agricultural University of Athens	AUA	STAR4BBS	Value chain selection & Trade Flows; CBA & Feasibility Study
Nikola	Matovic	Technical University of Berlin	TUB	STAR4BBS	JMS; Selection and review of CSLs
Luana	Ladu	Technical University of Berlin	TUB	STAR4BBS	JMS; Selection and review of CSLs
Kristin	Komives	ISEAL Alliance	ISEAL	STAR4BBS	JMS
Maira	Devisscher	ISEAL Alliance	ISEAL	STAR4BBS	JMS
Naomi	Black	ISEAL Alliance	ISEAL	STAR4BBS	JMS
Luciano	Proto Cassina	nova-Institute	NOVA	STAR4BBS	Value chain selection & Trade Flows

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Olaf	Porc	nova-Institute	NOVA	STAR4BBS	Value chain selection & Trade Flows
Enrica	Imbert	Sapienza University of Rome	UNITELMA	STAR4BBS	CBA & Feasibility Study; Selection and review of CSLs
Ana Gabriela	Encino	Sapienza University of Rome	UNITELMA	STAR4BBS	CBA & Feasibility Study; Selection and review of CSLs
Sara	Lago Olveira	University of Santiago de Compostela	USC	STAR4BBS	JMS; CBA & Feasibility Study
Maite	Moreira	University of Santiago de Compostela	USC	STAR4BBS	JMS; CBA & Feasibility Study
Ana	Arias Calvo	University of Santiago de Compostela	USC	STAR4BBS	JMS; CBA & Feasibility Study

Maria Carmela	Fierro	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea	APRE	STAR4BBS	Communication & Dissemination
Ilaria	Bientinesi	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea	APRE	STAR4BBS	Communication & Dissemination
Valeria	Mingardi	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea	APRE	STAR4BBS	Communication & Dissemination
Sara	Silvi	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea	APRE	STAR4BBS	Communication & Dissemination
Chiara	Pocaterra	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea	APRE	STAR4BBS	Communication & Dissemination
Blanca	De Ulibarri	Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials	RSB	STAR4BBS	JMS
Harmen	Willemse	Better Biomass	BetterBiomass	STAR4BBS	JMS

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Tilman	Denkler	Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und - Prüfung	BAM	STAR4BBS	JMS
Barbara	Palacino Blazquez	Centro de Investigacion de Recursos y Consumos Energeticos	CIRCE	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	Value chain selection & Trade Flows
Loek	Verwijst	Control Union	CU	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	CBA & Feasibility Study; JMS
Karolina	Niemenoja	Control Union	CU	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	CBA & Feasibility Study; JMS
Marxine	Waite	Environmental Coalition on Standards	ECOS	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	JMS
Mariana	López Dávila	Environmental Coalition on Standards	ECOS	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	JMS

Mathilde	Crêpy	Environmental Coalition on Standards	ECOS	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	JMS
Laura	Väyrynen	Environmental Coalition on Standards	ECOS	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	JMS
Luuk	Vissers	Wageningen University & Research	WR - WEcR	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	CBA & Feasibility Study
Lusine	Aramyan	Wageningen University & Research	WR - WEcR	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	CBA & Feasibility Study
Behrang	Manouchehrabadi	Wageningen University & Research	WR - WEcR	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	CBA & Feasibility Study
Myrna	van Leeuwen	Wageningen University & Research	WR - WEcR	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	Value chain selection & Trade Flows

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Iris	Vural Gürsel	Wageningen University & Research	WR - WFBR	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	JMS; Selection and review of CSLs
Heleen	Ballemans	Wageningen University & Research	WR - WFBR	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	JMS; Selection and review of CSLs
Heike	Axmann	Wageningen University & Research	WR - WFBR	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	JMS; Selection and review of CSLs
Annie	Kalimeri	WHITE Research	WHITE	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	Communication & Dissemination
Pinelopi	Kaslama	WHITE Research	WHITE	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	Communication & Dissemination

The collaboration among the three PCs and IPTs is an essential aspect of ensuring the success of the sister projects. Exchanging information through emails, online meetings, and a shared repository helps align key activities and report on progress to other IPT members. The ad-hoc and regular meetings within and among inter-project teams facilitate the planning and implementation of outputs, thereby avoiding repetition, overlap, and loss of important information. The involvement of the PCs in the coordination and management of the cluster activities is pivotal in ensuring effective communication with the Project Officers at REA. The joint effort of the IPTs leads to a more coherent and impactful approach towards achieving the objectives of the cluster projects.

2.2.3. Cluster exchange

Meetings are an essential part of project management and coordination, especially when it comes to sister projects that have a common goal. In addition, joint meetings allow project teams to discuss and align their activities, avoid duplication of work, and identify potential synergies between projects. Regular communication through periodic online meetings and email exchange helps to ensure that all parties are working towards the same objective.

The three cluster projects have already established regular communication and coordination through periodic meetings and extensive email exchange to meet these goals. In addition, ad-hoc meetings are also being conducted when needed to discuss various thematic areas and to identify potential synergies between the projects.

- Shared repository

A dedicated shared repository (i.e., SharePoint titled Horizon EU Cluster ZP-01-07) has been created and is accessible to all sister projects partners. In the repository, the cluster exchanges information, shares documents and relevant literature sources and works on joint deliverables. Each of the five thematic area has a dedicated sub-folder for inter-project collaboration. In these folders, the inter-project teams store joint working documents, presentations given during meetings, meeting minutes, and relevant literature. Additionally, each project places a copy of their submitted deliverables into a dedicated folder in this shared repository. Furthermore, documents related to the planning of joint communication and dissemination activities are maintained here. In communications between inter-project teams, all documents are stored in the Sharepoint and linked to in the e-mails rather than attaching them to the e-mails.

- PC and IPT meetings

Since the inception of the cluster, meetings have been held to ensure effective collaboration and coordination among the three sister projects. These meetings involve project coordinator calls, inter-project team calls, and meetings with Project Officer, among others. A variety of

topics are discussed in these meetings, ranging from the selection of value chains and sustainability criteria to the development of the Joint Monitoring System (JMS).

In June 2023, a meeting of the teams within sister projects that were working on the development of the JMS, was organised to follow up on each project's objectives and to discuss the next steps and align ongoing work. It was decided that sub-teams should be created to ensure efficient use of resources. Four sub-teams were formed: one for each of the three levels of the JMS (system, content, outcome) and one that would meet occasionally to discuss the evaluation structure of the JMS. Each sub-team has representation from all three sister projects. Core meetings that include all sub-teams are held periodically (every 6 weeks) and are led by the coordinators of the three sister projects. Each sub-team meeting is prepared and led by the sister project team responsible for the coordination of each level (i.e., STAR4BBS leads the system level, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED leads the content level and HARMONITOR leads the outcome level sub-team meetings). In addition, each sub-team is present at the other levels' meetings in accordance with their interest and expertise.

The three project coordinators agreed to meet every 6 weeks. However, ad-hoc additional meetings are organised when needed. Several meetings between project coordinators have been organized to discuss overall coordination, answer questions, and ensure the alignment of activities. In addition, PCs are continuously exchanging emails to discuss ongoing activities of the cluster.

The summary in Annex I provides a chronological overview of all meetings held between June 2022 and November 2023, outlining the purpose of each meeting.

2.3. Joint Strategic Areas

2.3.1. Explanation of the Joint Monitoring System (JMS) proposal and its development

The goal of the three sister projects working together to develop a Joint Monitoring System (JMS) is to reduce confusion, divergences, and mistrust among stakeholders by creating a harmonised, overarching system. This will bring coherence and clarity for policymakers driving the transition to a bioeconomy in the EU. Working together allows the projects to build on each other's knowledge and experience, subjecting the JMS to a higher level of scrutiny and maximising the effective use of resources. The JMS will streamline stakeholder consultations to maximize their impact and reduce fatigue while eliminating competition among the three projects and maximizing the synergies and impacts of the results. The creation of a JMS requires extensive coordination, but it is believed to be feasible and worthwhile to work together to

provide a more comprehensive and detailed tool, covering a wide range of bio-based sectors and products.

Actions being undertaken to achieve the aforementioned goal are as follows:

- **Defining the scope of the JMS:** The first step was to define the scope of the JMS by clearly defining the products and sectors to be covered and the geographical regions to be included in the analysis. This ensures that all the sister projects have a shared understanding of the scope of the JMS.
- **Proposing the structure of the JMS:** The JMS will be structured into three levels: system, content, and outcome, all with corresponding indicators. System indicators will focus on system characteristics, such as how a scheme is governed and how the standards or labels are developed. Content indicators will clarify the requirements of the CSLs vis-à-vis specific environmental, social, economic, and circularity priorities and targets. Outcome indicators will aim to capture the impact of the schemes and labels.
- **Testing and refining the JMS:** After the JMS framework has been developed, the next step is to test and refine the system by applying it to a range of previously selected CSLs. This will involve analysing the results and refining the methodology as needed.
- **Building stakeholder engagement:** Throughout the development and testing of the JMS, it is important to build stakeholder involvement to ensure that the JMS meets the needs of relevant stakeholders. A variety of stakeholder groups are involved in the development of the different elements of the JMS. This is done by engaging with policymakers, industry actors, NGOs, and other stakeholders to gather feedback and incorporate it into the JMS. In particular, joint events are organised by the three projects (for example, STAR4BBS organizes specific co-creation workshops).
- **Developing dissemination and communication strategies:** Once the JMS has been developed and tested, the next step is to develop dissemination and communication strategies to ensure that the JMS is widely adopted and used beyond the life of the sister projects. This will involve developing outreach materials and engaging with key stakeholders to promote the use of the JMS.

Overall, the key strategy for achieving the goal of developing a JMS is for the three sister projects to collaborate closely, leveraging their respective knowledge and experience to develop a comprehensive and effective system. By aligning on the scope, KPIs, and methodology for the JMS, and by engaging with stakeholders throughout the process, the three sister projects can

work together to develop a tool that has the potential to be widely adopted and used beyond the life of the projects.

The result will be a comprehensive and detailed tool that can be used to assess the sustainability of biobased products and support the transition to a bioeconomy in the EU.

Table 3 summarizes the proposed timeline for the development and testing of the JMS.

Table 3: Proposed timeline for the JMS planning and development

Task	Timelines
JMS proposal development	Dec 2022 - January 2023
JMS proposal presentation to European Commission (EC) Project Officers	February 2023
JMS proposal refinement and finalization, based on PO input	February/March 2023
Development of draft criteria (system, content, outcome)	March 2023 – January 2024
Co-creation workshop selection of CSLs. Partially linked to the JMS (STAR4BBS)	May/June 2023
Stakeholder engagement – joint side event as part of European Biomass Conference (EUBCE) in Bologna. At this event, the cluster presented the outcomes of the HARMONITOR stakeholder consultation and collected further input on the requirements for the JMS	June 2023
First draft of the JMS	January 2024
EC Policy officers' workshop on draft JMS (proposed, to be coordinated with Project Officers)	January 2024 (proposed)
Testing of the JMS (stakeholder engagement+ pilot audits + testing on CSLs) + Improvement of the JMS with feedback	Feb 24 – May 25
Final version of the JMS	May 2025

2.3.1.1. *Proposed division of responsibilities among the three projects*

All three projects are working on the conceptualisation and development of all the elements and levels of the JMS, respecting the work packages and tasks described in the grant agreement of each project. To systematically collect the inputs from the three projects in a strategic way, it was considered important to have each project coordinate one level. Thus, the cluster proposed an allocation of the coordination roles based on the strengths of each project and the partners involved.

STAR4BBS leads the development of the system level, supported by the knowledge and practical experience of project partner ISEAL in defining the credibility in sustainability systems. ISEAL's Codes of Good Practice cover many relevant aspects such as standard-setting and credible assurance processes. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED leads the content level, focusing on sustainability criteria with project partners WR and ECOS heavily involved. WR has been working on reviewing and analysing circularity criteria for biobased products to monitor progress seen in CSLs. As an environmental protection organisation working on, among others, EU sustainable product policy such as the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation, ECOS has strong expertise on environmental and circularity matters. Between 2020 and 2022, ECOS was also a member of the Platform on Sustainable Finance, and as an appointed circular economy expert, follows various bioeconomy-related activities to be included in Taxonomy delegated acts. HARMONITOR is leading the outcome level as the WP leader, and UU as an academic organisation has activities planned to tackle the assessment of the effectiveness of CSLs. The outcome level is currently the least explored area in research and as such allows for methodological development and venturing beyond conventional methods.

Each sister project is working jointly to develop the JMS. Under the leadership of one sister project in each level (as described above), each sister project provides inputs on the conceptualization of the content of each level using their project proposal as a guide to determine what aspects to focus on. The three projects also work jointly in the interpretation component of the JMS (Table 4), proposing minimum requirements of the different indicators and related evaluation mechanism.

Table 4: Contributions of sister projects to the JMS development

Project	Contribution to the activity
STAR4BBS	Coordination of the system level of the JMS. Development of the set of principles, criteria and indicators for the

	<p>system characteristics, through consortia expertise, literature review, legislations, review of monitoring systems. System characteristics are structured into four categories: governance and scheme management; standard setting; assurance; traceability and claims.</p> <p>Contribution to the content level of the JMS, through produced deliverables D3.1ⁱ and D3.2ⁱⁱ and through participation in the meetings and providing feedback.</p> <p>Contribution to the outcome level of the JMS, through participation in the meetings, inputs from D1.3ⁱⁱⁱ and providing literature from own research. Coordination and conceptualization of the Evaluation structure (with contribution from the D4.1^{iv}).</p>
SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	<p>Coordination of the content level of the JMS. Development of the sustainability principles, criteria and indicators, through review of relevant legislations, standards, guidelines and monitoring tools, structured into four dimensions: economic, environmental, social and circularity. Collection of feedback and input from internal partners as well as partners from the sister projects. Arrangement of meetings with the content level sub-group team composed of members from the three projects to present progress and discuss key comments or aspects. Processing of feedback received into development of final draft versions. Presenting this as input for external stakeholder engagement and for testing with the CSLs and pilot auditing. Additionally, contribution to the system and outcome level of the JMS and to the design of the evaluation mechanism through produced deliverable D1.2 and D3.1 and through participation in the meetings and providing feedback.</p>
HARMONITOR	<p>Coordination of the outcome level of the JMS. Development of the methodology to define and monitor the progress of CSLs towards measurable outcomes over time, including selection of a limited number of criteria and indicators (in</p>

close coordination the outcome and system level), inventory of available self-reported and 3rd party evidence, and potential set up of a draft evaluation structure to assess the progress of an indicator. Collection of feedback and input from internal partners as well as partners from the sister projects. Arrangement of meetings with the content level sub-group team composed of members from the three projects to present progress and discuss key comments or aspects. Processing of feedback received into development of final draft versions. Presenting this as input for external stakeholder engagement and for testing with the CSLs and pilot auditing.

Stakeholder engagement will be continued throughout different phases of the monitoring system development. The three projects will have joint workshops where they will present and ask for feedback on the JMS. They will jointly work to optimise the JMS by incorporating relevant inputs. In addition, the JMS will be tested on a jointly selected set of CSLs. The intention is that this selection of CSLs will cover the most prominent CSLs and a broad range of sectors in the biobased industry. The feedback from this testing process will also be used in optimising the JMS. Furthermore, pilot testing will be carried out to provide feedback in terms of practical applicability of the requirements of the JMS.

2.3.2. Joint Advisory Board

Formation of a Joint Advisory Board (JAB)

To streamline communication and receive feedback from a wider range of experts, the three projects have decided to establish one Joint Advisory Board (JAB) instead of separate boards for each project. The three PCs created a list of possible members of the JAB by considering the members already contacted during proposal preparation (Table 5). The potential members were contacted, and all expressed willingness to join the JAB.

The board is comprised of experts from academia and international organisations with expertise in, for example, industrial bio-based value chains and sustainability systems. The JAB advises on and provides guidance related to the implementation of relevant project activities as well as specific tasks. The JAB also monitors and critically reviews the projects' development and progress in meeting their objectives, advises on long-term and short-term strategic decisions, and facilitates connection with targeted stakeholder groups.

Purpose and benefits of the Joint Advisory Board

The JAB serves as a valuable resource for the three projects. With a diverse range of expertise and representation of various stakeholder categories, the board provides advice and guidance on a range of topics including sustainability certification schemes and labels for bio-based systems, monitoring systems for assessing the effectiveness of existing certification schemes and labels, and sustainability policy targets. Additionally, the board helps the cluster stay up to date with the latest developments related to the project and facilitates connections with targeted stakeholders. The JAB brings alignment with ongoing international efforts and contributes to the wider dissemination of project results with relevant stakeholders via their network, thereby supporting the sustainability of project outcomes beyond the project lifetime.

Coordination of activities related to the Joint Advisory Board

The JAB members participate in board meetings (aimed to be organised at least once a year) as well as in stakeholder engagement activities organised by the cluster projects, providing feedback on research findings and bringing input relevant for the research conducted. The JAB provides feedback and advice based on members' knowledge and expertise. Membership in the JAB is voluntary and unremunerated, with no contractual obligation but demonstrating a commitment to cooperate, actively participate, and provide advice. The membership lasts for the entire duration of the projects (36 months), and members may request their membership to be terminated at any time in writing. The JAB has the duty to protect all confidential and non-public information, such as draft versions of project deliverables, preliminary findings or contents of the discussions within the meetings.

Board meetings are organized online or on-site, based on agreement among the sister projects PCs. The first meeting was organised in an online setting on 24th of February 2023. This JAB kick-off meeting aimed to introduce the inter-project teams and present the projects' goals. This was followed by a short introduction to two topics of interest (development of a joint monitoring system and selection of biobased value chains) to obtain JAB's input and feedback.

The PCs notify JAB about any upcoming meetings and events at least three weeks in advance. A draft agenda is shared with JAB members in advance.

The deliverable D7.2 from the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project and D8.1 from the STAR4BBS project includes all the terms of reference, rules, and confidentiality provisions related to the Joint Advisory Board. The members of the JAB can be found on each project-specific website and the lists are updated in the case of any changes in the composition of the JAB.

Table 5: Contribution of sister projects to establishing a Joint Advisory Board

Name	Affiliation	Expertise	Contacted by
Ms. Constance Ißbrücker	DIN CERTCO	Manager Certified Products, among others responsible for Sustainability of bioplastics and Standardisation and certification of bioplastics	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED
Mr. Mario Bonaccorso	SPRING - Italian Circular Bioeconomy Cluster	Cluster Manager at SPRING, development of biobased industries in Italy in a sustainable way with a focus on regional territorial players	STAR4BBS
Dr. Audrun Utskarpen	Ecolabelling Norway	Senior Environmental Advisor, among others knowledge on ecolabels and their role in reducing the environmental impact of products	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED
Mr. Santiago Fernandez De Cordoba	United Nations Forum on Sustainability Standards (UNFSS)	Coordinator of the UNFSS, head UNCTAD Sustainability Standards Program analysing potential effectiveness and development impact of sustainability	STAR4BBS

		schemes from the perspectives of developing-countries	
Mr. Marco Rupp	Bio-based Industries Consortium (BIC)	Public Affairs & Sustainability Manager	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED
Ms. Jenny Walthher-Thoss	Berndt+Partner Consultants	Senior Consultant Sustainability, expertise in sustainability standards and certification, sustainable biomass and supply chains	STAR4BBS
Dr. Martin Greimel	University of Natural Resources and Life Science Vienna	Head of the Center for Bioeconomy, coordination of all bioeconomy related research	HARMONITOR
Mr. Bernard de Galembert	CEFIC - European Chemical Industry Council	Sector Group Manager	HARMONITOR
Ms. Ciara McCarthy	Consulting company	Owner	HARMONITOR
Textile Exchange	NGO	Non-profit organisation driving positive action on climate change across the fashion, textile, and apparel industry	STAR4BBS

2.4. Joint Dissemination Activities

Effective cooperation among projects is crucial in achieving shared goals and maximising impact. The three projects can engage in various cooperation activities, such as exchange of information, thematic area discussions, coordination of activities, and dissemination and communication. For all joint dissemination activities, all three sister projects are invited to participate, and active feedback and opinions are valued and welcomed from all projects.

The three projects are working together to disseminate their findings and results to a wider audience. This includes joint publications, presentations, and outreach activities with the goal of promoting the importance of sustainability in bio-based systems. This ensures that the three projects are aligned in their messaging and that confusion and inconsistency are avoided.

As part of the dissemination and communication strategy, the three sister projects attend various events, such as workshops and conferences, where they present their findings, activities, and outputs (Figure 2). Working together, they create joint presentations that showcase the collective impact of their work, highlighting the importance of sustainability in bio-based systems. This collaborative approach ensures that their messaging is consistent and aligned.

List of joint activities undertaken:

- ✓ Establishing dedicated sections on each project's website referring to sister projects
- ✓ Incorporating exclusive entries in newsletters to promote sister projects
- ✓ Actively engaging with and promoting the social media accounts of and news concerning each project
- ✓ Collaboratively organising the first Joint Advisory Board meeting
- ✓ Co-hosting the first engagement and promotional event within the context of the EUBCE conference in 2023
- ✓ Collaborating on a joint application for the Horizon Results Booster services module A and B.
- ✓ Participation of all three project representatives in the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Network of Interest. Featuring dedicated interviews with project coordinators on the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project website.
- ✓ Supporting and attending events of other sister projects
- ✓ Developing a shared events calendar to effectively engage relevant stakeholders without overburdening them.

Our synergies...

Meet our sister projects, HARMONITOR and STAR4BBS! What do all three projects have in common? They aim to improve the certification systems of biobased products.

HARMONITOR's team aims to improve the effectiveness of certification schemes and labels in different sectors of the European Bioeconomy. Explore [more](#) about the project!

STAR4BBS's team works on the development of indicators and a new monitoring system for assessing the effectiveness and robustness of existing European Sustainability Certification Schemes and labels related to biological feedstock and biobased products. Explore more about STAR4BBS by following the project on [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#).

All three projects work under the same vision and contribute to a faster green transition! Stay tuned to find out more about our joint events and activities!!

Figure 2: Cluster events disseminated through social media networks

The Table 6 indicates the events co-organised, supported and participated in by all three projects.

Table 6: Co-organized, supported and co- participated events

Event	Description
Advisory Board meeting	The first Joint Advisory Board meeting was co-organised by all three projects. All Joint Advisory Board members introduced themselves while the advancements of the project were presented and an open discussion providing valuable feedback followed.
1st Joint Engagement Event on Sustainability Certification of Biobased Products	Co-organisation of the first engagement and promotional event in the framework of EUBCE 2023 (the 31st edition of the European Biomass Conference & Exhibition), in Bologna, Italy (5-9th June 2023).

Robust and Effective Sustainability Certification for Bio-based Systems	BiobasedCert cluster online co-creation event (11th of December 2023), the first draft of the JMS will be presented to stakeholders for their feedback. This will represent the first of the upcoming consultations on collecting stakeholders' input.
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Horizon Results Booster (HRB) services

In an effort to strengthen collaboration, develop a common dissemination strategy, and establish a unified identity for the three projects for events and result dissemination, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's dissemination team applied for HRB services on behalf of all three projects following communication with all sister projects. The consortium received approval to access services from both Module A and Module B.

Module A: *Identifying and creating the portfolio of R&I project results:* This module supports the creation of a portfolio of results that is suitable for joint dissemination. It also includes a comprehensive mapping of the relevant stakeholders/target audience for each particular portfolio.

Module B: *Helping projects from the portfolio to design and execute a portfolio dissemination plan:* This module focuses on supporting the cluster group to design a joint dissemination plan for the portfolio and carry out the actual dissemination of the results. The service deliverable includes the visual identity for the beneficiary project group and a short video describing the project results.

After meetings with service representatives and internal discussions among project representatives, Module A was conducted from June 2023 to September 2023, resulting in a report titled 'Portfolio of Research and Innovation Results' (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Module A report

Module B was initiated immediately after the completion of Module A, starting in September 2023. During this phase, the cluster evaluates the production of several key promotional materials, including:

- Development of a shared project identity
- Creation of a template for joint deliverables
- Production of a short video introducing all three projects
- Design of a common factsheet

Project group: BiobasedCert - Enhancing Sustainability Certification Schemes and Labels for Bio-based Systems

BiobasedCert Cluster is a group of three European projects, engaged in the development and testing of monitoring systems to assess the effectiveness and reliability of international and EU sustainability certification schemes and labels.

Figure 4: Cluster's joint logo

First joint engagement and promotional event in the EUBCE 2023:

On the 7th of June 2023, the cluster's first joint event (led by HARMONITOR) took place at the European Biomass Conference and Exhibition (EUBCE), in Bologna, Italy. This event, known as the 1st Joint Engagement Event on Sustainability Certification of Biobased Products, was jointly organised by SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, HARMONITOR, and STAR4BBS. Drawing over 75 participants, the event gathered diverse stakeholders, including industry experts, sustainability system actors, academic scholars, regional bioeconomy stakeholders, citizens, members of civic society, and representatives from other esteemed EU initiatives. This hybrid event served as an opportunity for the three sister projects to shed light on their respective missions, areas of research, and approaches concerning sustainability certification (Figure 5).

Figure 5: EUBCE hybrid event

Organisation of the joint co-creation workshop in December 2023:

The cluster aims to organise a series of joint events, starting with an online co-creation workshop (led by STAR4BBS) on 11th December 2023.

The HARMONITOR, STAR4BBS and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED projects have received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme

This co-creation workshop will bring together stakeholders and experts to share key findings, receive valuable input and suggestions, and explore potential collaborations. The topics of the workshop are as follows:

- The Joint Monitoring System for sustainability certification schemes and labels for bio-based systems:
 - Updates on the collaborative efforts towards defining indicators to be included in the JMS for assessing the robustness and effectiveness of sustainability certification schemes and labels
 - Proposal for evaluation structure of the JMS
- Collaborative platform for sustainability certification schemes and labels: Update on the concept for a platform that fosters collaboration among certification schemes and labels, promoting synergy and efficiency in the industry.

By undertaking all previously mentioned cooperation activities, the three projects are working together effectively to achieve their shared goals and maximise the impact of their work.

3. Potential Barriers

In any collaborative project involving multiple stakeholders, there are bound to be potential barriers that may hinder the completion of the steps identified in the action plan. One potential barrier is disagreements or controversies among the partners. In such cases, it is important to have a clear dispute resolution mechanism in place that ensures a fair and equitable solution for all parties involved. This mechanism has been agreed upon in a consensus-based manner by all three project coordinators at the outset of the collaboration and is outlined in the framework for collaboration.

Another potential barrier is a lack of commitment from external stakeholders (e.g., Joint Advisory Board members). It is essential that relevant stakeholders are committed and open to collaboration and are willing to contribute time, resources, and expertise to the execution of joint activities. If important stakeholders are not fully committed to the collaboration, it could lead to delays, conflicts, and an inability to achieve the desired outcomes. To address this potential barrier, the consortium aims to ensure that all stakeholders understand the value and benefits of the collaboration and have a clear understanding of their roles and responsibilities. In addition, by joining forces, the three projects count on a broader network of stakeholders that can support the cluster activities.

Finally, differences in organisational culture, communication styles, and working practices among the cluster project teams could also be potential barriers to collaboration. To address these potential barriers, it is important to establish clear lines of communication, set expectations for working practices and communication styles, and provide support to partners as needed. This could involve developing a shared vocabulary, providing cultural sensitivity training by the coordinators, and promoting open communication at all times.

4. Next activities

As mentioned before, joint events will be organized by the cluster based on the mutual decision which resulted in aligning joint activities and responsibilities for organisation and lead role, as indicated in Table 7.

Table 7: Alignment of dissemination and communication activities of three sister projects

Month	HARMONITOR	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	STAR4BBS	Decision - Joint Activities	Project responsible
December-23	Task 2.4 - First meeting with CSLs participating in platform - Discussion findings and feedback	Workshop (no2) - Participants: CSLs + policymakers - Objective: get input on the draft JMS before the testing phase (WP3, T3.2 and WP5 T5.2)	3rd co-creation workshop (WP6) - collect stakeholder input on the 1st draft of the JMS, including evaluation structure	Meeting with CSLs- Co-creation workshop on the JMS (include policymakers)- Early December	STAR4BBS
March-24	Task 7.4 - Second topic webinar to present topics of interest - open to all CSLs	Workshop (no3) - Cost benefit analysis, pilot auditing (WP4)	4th co-creation workshop on costs and benefits analysis	Event: Co-creation workshop Cost benefits and feasibility - Mid February	STAR4BBS
March-24	Task 7.4 - First topic webinar to present topics of interest - open to all CSLs (topics to choose from: trade flows,	Workshop (no4)- Global trade flow analysis (WP2, T2.2)		Event: Global trade flow analysis	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

The HARMONITOR, STAR4BBS and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED projects have received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme

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	comparison of CSLs, monitoring system, costs and benefits)				
May-24	Task 2.4 - Second meeting with CSLs participating in platform - Discussion findings and feedback	Workshop (no5) - Testing of JMS, engagement & feedback (T3.3, T3.4, T3.5)		Event: Co-creation event with CSLs+ policymakers + monitoring tool owners + NGOs, feedback on JMS application (part 1)	HARMONITOR
June-24	Task 7.4 - Third topic webinar to present topics of interest - open to all CSLs	2nd Engagement event - Joint side event as part of the EUBCE conference, 24-27 June in Marseille, France		Joint event: EUBCE Conference	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED
September-24	Task 2.4 - Third meeting with CSLs participating in Platform - Discussion findings and feedback	Workshop (no6) - Testing of JMS engagement/feedback (T3.3, T3.4, T3.5)	5th co-creation workshop	Event: 5th co-creation workshop, feedback on JMS application (part 2)	STAR4BBS

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October-24	Task 7.4 - Fourth topic webinar to present topics of interest - open to all CSLs	Workshop (no7) - Engagement with industry for adoption of robust/effective schemes (T5.4)	Barriers in data collection	Joint Webinar/training: Analysis of barriers	HARMONITOR
November-24	Task 4.3 - Workshop/meeting with CSLs -Validation of comparison of selected CSLs	Workshop (no8) - Engagement with CSLs (T5.3)		Meeting: CSL comparison (preliminary) with Network of Interest	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED
February-25	Task 6.4 - Focus groups to identify governance options for increasing certified production Task 7.4 - Fifth topic webinar - topics of interest	Workshop (no9) - Engagement with policymakers, industry to increase adoption (T5.2, T5.4)	6th co-creation workshop	Event: Workshop - Governance options /recommendations for increasing uptake (part 1)	HARMONITOR
April-25	Task 2.4 - Fourth meeting with CSLs participating in Platform - Discussion findings and feedback	Workshop (no10) - Engagement with CSLs + industry + regional actors for adoption of		Event: Workshop - JMS Governance options /recommendations	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

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		robust/effective schemes (T5.3, T5.4, T5.5)		for increasing uptake (part 2)		
May-25	Task 7.4 - Final event	3rd Engagement event - Final event in Brussels, Belgium	Virtual meeting involving different stakeholders to discuss recommendations (M34-M35)	Final event in Brussels	STAR4BBS	
June-25						
July-25						
August-25						

5. Conclusions

The consolidation of the BiobasedCert cluster, encompassing the STAR4BBS, HARMONITOR, and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED projects, marks a significant stride in aligning with the objectives of the various projects. By establishing a collaborative framework and undertaking joint initiatives, the cluster has effectively fostered communication and development to better address the goals set forth in the Horizon Europe call for conducting research on sustainability certification schemes in bio-based systems.

This report summarises the collaborative efforts outlined during the initial establishment of the cluster, coupled with the delineation of upcoming joint activities. These activities underscore the clusters' commitment to strengthening the interconnectivity between the three projects. Noteworthy strategic areas of shared importance are identified, each accompanied by specified cooperation activities. The inter-project teams are dedicated to the five thematic areas that were identified in the projects (selection and review of CSLs; bio-based value chain selection and global trade flows; Joint Monitoring System; analysis of costs and benefits and feasibility study; communication and dissemination of the results). The creation of a Joint Advisory Board and the Joint Monitoring System are standout features, facilitating the exchange of expertise and feedback, as well as boosted efforts, to enhance the robustness of sustainability certification schemes.

In conclusion, the establishment of the BiobasedCert cluster reflects a positive progression aligned with the mid-term objectives and plans outlined in the clustering report. The sustained collaboration among project coordinators and inter-project teams is instrumental for effective implementation. The strategic identification of shared areas and cooperation activities serves as a guiding framework, outlining the necessary steps to fortify the connections between the three projects and realize desired outcomes. The BiobasedCert cluster not only signals a united commitment to common objectives but also sets the stage for continued collaboration, ensuring the enduring impact of collective endeavours.

Annex I

CLUSTER MEETINGS

General meetings

- 16th June 2022: Joint kick-off meeting of three sister projects and REA representative. Goal: Target synergies between projects and align the work on maximising the potential of sustainability CSLs to support a successful transition to a sustainable bio-based economy.
- 17th January 2023: Meeting with the Policy Officers and Project Officer focused on the proposal for JMS
- 17th February 2023: Meeting with the PO to present the strategy and idea around the JMS
- 24th February 2023: Kick-off meeting of the Joint Advisory Board
- 7th June 2023: EUBCE Side event jointly organized titled Sustainability certification of bio-based products

Projects Coordinators meetings

- 27th September 2022: First PC meeting.
- 7th October 2022: Coordinators' catch-up call (after Project2Project meeting in Brussels, Belgium).
- 4th and 11th November 2022: Coordinators' meetings for organizing and planning the HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION meeting of the 14th of November 2022 (with Policy Officers and Project Officer).
- 16th January 2023: Coordinators' meeting for preparation for the meeting of 17th January 2023 with the Project Officer of REA.
- 20th and 25th January 2023: Coordinators' meetings to finalise the strategy of the JMS, discuss the potential Joint Advisory Board members, and planning the first meeting with them.
- 16th February 2023: Meeting of the PCs for preparation for the meeting of the 17th February 2023 with the Project Officer of REA.
- 22nd March 2023 Coordinators catch up call
- 8th May 2023 Coordinators catch up call
- 22nd August 2023 Coordinators catch up call
- 13th September 2023: Coordinators discussion on joint events/workshops planning
- 9th October 2023: Coordinators catch up call

IPT meetingsIPT Bio-based value chain selection and global trade flows

- 14th October 2022: First meeting of the team Bio-based value chain selection and analysis of trade flows
- 28th October 2022: Joint sister project meeting with participants from the HARMONITOR, SUSCERT4BIOBASED and STAR4BBS (Topic: value chain selection, based on the development of the draft methodology taking into account the approach and results of the BTG value chain selection within the HARMONITOR project)
- 14th November 2022: Joint sister project meeting on value chains selection
- 8th December 2022: Joint sister project meeting on selected value chains

IPT Joint Monitoring System + Selection and review of CSLs

- 12th October 2022: First meeting of the team for the Development of the monitoring system
- 17th October 2022: Meeting between HARMONITOR and STAR4BBS on Identification and selection of CSLs
- 9th November 2022: Meeting between three inter-consortia teams for Defining the purpose of the JMS
- 16th November 2022: Meeting on Review and analysis of CSL criteria and indicators.
- 8th and 12th December 2022: Meetings between sister project core teams on Preparation of the proposal for JMS
- 19th December 2022: Meeting with all three sister project teams working on the joint monitoring system.
- 11th and 19th January 2023: Final JMS proposal discussions.
- 20th February 2023: Meeting with ITC Standards Map
- 16th June 2023: JMS 1st core team meeting
- 26th June 2023: System level kick-off meeting
- 29th June 2023: JMS content level sub-team 1st meeting
- 3rd July 2023: Outcome level kick-off meeting
- 25th July 2023: System level meeting
- 18th August 2023: Outcome level meeting
- 24th August 2023: System level meeting
- 28th August 2023: JMS content level sub-team 2nd meeting
- 28th August 2023: Outcome level meeting
- 1st September 2023: JMS 2nd core team meeting
- 21st September 2023: JMS - content level - economic dimension meeting

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- 25th September 2023: JMS content level sub-team 3rd meeting
- 25th September 2023: System level meeting
- 4th October 2023: Evaluation structure kick-off meeting
- 11th October 2023: JMS 3rd core team meeting
- 12th October 2023: JMS - content level - social dimension meeting
- 17th October 2023: Outcome level meeting
- 25th October 2023: JMS content level sub-team 4th meeting
- 31st October 2023: System level meeting
- 2nd November 2023: Follow-up JMS - content level - social dimension meeting
- 13th November 2023: JMS content level sub-team 5th meeting
- 13th November 2023: Outcome level meeting
- 15th November 2023: JMS II Evaluation structure meeting
- 22nd November 2023: JMS 4th core team meeting
- 28th November 2023: System level meeting

IPT Costs, benefits and economic feasibility

- 10th October 2022: First meeting of the team Costs, benefits and economic feasibility
- 5th December 2022: Second meeting of the team Costs, benefits, and economic feasibility of sustainability certification
- 15th February 2023: Third meeting of the team Costs, benefits, and economic feasibility.
- 25th May 2023: Fourth meeting of the team Costs, benefits, and economic feasibility.
- 12th September 2023: Fifth meeting of the team Costs, benefits, and economic feasibility
- 29th November 2023: Sixth meeting of the team Costs, benefits, and economic feasibility

IPT Communication & Dissemination

Horizon Results Booster Services (HRB)

- 19th June 2023
- 31st July 2023
- 19th September 2023

BiobasedCert events preparation meetings

- 16th October 2023: Cluster co-creation event on JMS
- 6th November 2023: Cluster co-creation event on JMS
- 21st November 2023: Cluster co-creation event on JMS

- i STAR4BBS (2023) Deliverable D3.1 Report on sustainability indicators for the monitoring system based on Life Cycle Assessment
- ii STAR4BBS (2023) Deliverable D3.2 Report on additional indicators of monitoring system
- iii STAR4BBS (2023): Deliverable D1.3 Report on impact and contribution of existing SCS and B2B Labels
- iv STAR4BBS (2023): Deliverable D4.1 Concept of the monitoring system

